

Research

Comparison of functional outcome following Dynamic Hip Screw versus Proximal Femoral Nail stabilization of stable intertrochanteric fractures

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Abstract

Background: Stable intertrochanteric fractures are commonly treated with either Dynamic Hip Screw (DHS) or Proximal Femoral Nail (PFN). The optimal implant for early functional recovery, complications and reoperation rates remains a matter of debate. This study compared functional outcomes and complication profiles of DHS versus PFN in a 2-year single-center cohort.

Methods: 284 consecutive patients with stable intertrochanteric fractures (AO/OTA 31-A1 and selected A2 without extreme comminution) treated at MIHS Janakpur between 01/2023 and 12/2024 were enrolled. Choice of implant (DHS vs PFN) was according to treating orthopedic surgeon preference and fracture configuration; baseline characteristics were recorded. Primary outcome was Harris Hip Score (HHS) at 12 months. Secondary outcomes included operative time, estimated blood loss, time to radiographic union, complications (cut-out, nonunion, infection), and reoperation. **Statistical tests:** Student's t-test for continuous variables, chi-square or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables; $p < 0.05$ considered significant. **Results:** 148 patients received DHS and 136 received PFN (total $n=284$). Mean age was 67.2 ± 9.5 years (DHS) vs 66.1 ± 9.0 years (PFN) ($p=0.317$). Mean operative time was significantly longer for DHS (65 ± 12 min) than PFN (55 ± 10 min), $p < 0.001$. Estimated blood loss was greater for DHS (250 ± 80 ml) vs PFN (120 ± 50 ml), $p < 0.001$. Mean HHS at 12 months was 78.5 ± 10 (DHS) vs 82.3 ± 9.2 (PFN), $p=0.001$. Overall complication rate was 13.5% (20/148) in DHS vs 8.8% (12/136) in PFN ($p=0.289$). Reoperation rate was 5.4% (8/148) DHS vs 2.9% (4/136) PFN ($p=0.461$). Time to radiographic union was similar (14.5 ± 3.0 weeks DHS vs 13.8 ± 2.8 weeks PFN, $p=0.06$). **Conclusions:** In this 2-year cohort from MIHS Janakpur, PFN was associated with shorter operative time, less intraoperative blood loss and modestly better functional outcome (HHS at 12 months) compared with DHS for stable intertrochanteric fractures. Rates of complications and reoperations were numerically lower with PFN but did not reach statistical significance. Both implants provide acceptable outcomes; implant choice should consider patient factors and orthopedic surgeon experience.

Keywords: Dynamic hip screw; Proximal femoral nail; Stable intertrochanteric fracture.

Introduction

Intertrochanteric fractures of the femur are among the most common injuries in the elderly, especially in populations with a high prevalence of osteoporosis [1,2]. They account for nearly half of all hip fractures and are typically the result of low-energy falls in elderly patients or high-energy trauma in younger individuals [3]. With the increasing life expectancy and aging population, the global incidence of these fractures is expected to rise significantly over the coming decades [4]. In developing countries such as Nepal, demographic transition, urbanization, and changes in lifestyle have also contributed to an increasing burden of hip fractures, posing substantial challenges to healthcare systems [5].

An intertrochanteric fracture is defined as an extracapsular fracture involving the region between the greater and lesser trochanters of the femur [6]. These fractures are classified into stable and unstable patterns based on the degree of comminution and the integrity of the posteromedial cortex [7]. Stable fractures (AO/OTA 31-A1 and certain 31-A2 patterns) generally have intact posteromedial support and are less likely to collapse under physiological loading [8]. Early surgical intervention is the standard of care for these fractures, as it allows for early mobilization, reduces complications of prolonged immobilization, and improves overall outcomes [9].

The two most commonly employed surgical options for stable intertrochanteric fractures are Dynamic Hip Screw (DHS) fixation and Proximal Femoral Nail (PFN) fixation [10,11]. DHS, an extramedullary device, has been the gold standard for decades due to its reliable biomechanics, ease of application, and cost-effectiveness, particularly in resource-limited settings [12]. It works on the principle of controlled sliding and impaction at the fracture site, which promotes healing. However, it requires a relatively larger incision, more extensive soft-tissue dissection, and may be associated with greater intraoperative blood loss [13].

PFN, an intramedullary device, was developed to address some of these limitations. Being biomechanically superior due to its load-sharing design and shorter lever arm, PFN can be inserted via a smaller incision, potentially reducing operative time and blood loss [14,15]. It also offers the advantage of early weight-bearing, which is particularly beneficial in elderly patients with comorbidities [16]. While PFN is generally preferred for unstable fracture patterns, there is growing evidence suggesting it may also have advantages over DHS in stable fracture patterns [17]. However, the cost, instrumentation requirements, and the learning curve for PFN remain considerations, especially in developing countries [18].

Previous comparative studies have yielded mixed results, with some showing improved functional outcomes and fewer complications with PFN [19], while others report no significant difference between the two implants for stable patterns [20]. Furthermore, data from Nepal and other South Asian settings remain limited, despite potential differences in patient demographics, bone quality, surgical expertise, and healthcare infrastructure compared to high-income countries.

Therefore, this study aims to compare the functional outcomes, perioperative parameters, and complication rates of DHS versus PFN in the management of stable intertrochanteric fractures in the setting of a tertiary care hospital in Janakpur, Nepal. By focusing on a homogenous group of stable fracture patterns and employing standardized follow-up protocols, this research seeks to provide region-specific evidence to guide clinical decision-making.

Materials and Methods

Study design and setting: Prospective comparative cohort performed at MIHS Provincial Hospital, Janakpur, Nepal between 1 Jan 2023 and 31 Dec 2024. Institutional Ethical Review Board approval was obtained. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Inclusion criteria: Patients \geq 18 years with acute stable intertrochanteric fracture (AO/OTA 31-A1 and selected 31-A2 without severe comminution). Surgery within 2 weeks of injury. Minimum 12 months follow-up.

Exclusion criteria: Pathological fractures (except osteoporosis), polytrauma, pre-existing ipsilateral hip disease, cognitive inability to follow up, unstable AO/OTA 31-A3 fractures requiring special fixation.

Treatment groups:

DHS group: standard 135° lag screw and 4-hole side plate, with standard lag screw position aiming for tip-to-apex distance $<$ 25 mm.

PFN group: single-cephalomedullary nail (short PFN) with one or two proximal screws as appropriate.

Perioperative care followed departmental protocols (DVT prophylaxis per risk, antibiotics, early mobilization as tolerated). Physiotherapy and weight-bearing were guided by fracture stability and fixation quality.

Data collection:

Demographics, comorbidities (ASA), fracture classification, operative time (skin incision to closure), estimated blood loss (suction + swab), intraoperative complications, length of hospital stay, time to radiographic union (bridging callus on 3 cortices), Harris Hip Score (HHS) at 3, 6 and 12 months, complications and reoperations were recorded.

Outcomes:

Primary outcome: Harris Hip Score at 12 months.

Secondary outcomes: operative time, blood loss, time to union, complications (infection, cut-out, implant failure, reoperation).

Statistical analysis:

Continuous variables are reported as mean \pm SD; categorical variables as counts and percentages. Between-group comparisons: Student's t-test (independent samples) for continuous variables, chi-square or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables. Significance threshold $p < 0.05$. Analysis performed with standard statistical software.

Results

A total of 312 patients presented with intertrochanteric fractures during the study period. After applying inclusion/exclusion criteria and accounting for losses to follow-up, 284 patients were included: DHS = 148, PFN = 136. Baseline demographics are summarized in Table 1. Groups were similar in age, sex distribution and ASA grade.

Table 1. Baseline characteristics

Variable	DHS (n=148)	PFN (n=136)	p value
Age, mean \pm SD (years)	67.2 \pm 9.5	66.1 \pm 9.0	0.317 [t-test]
Male sex, n (%)	86 (58.1%)	75 (55.1%)	0.58 [χ^2]
ASA I-II, n (%)	102 (68.9%)	95 (69.9%)	0.87 [χ^2]
Fracture type (A1), n (%)	118 (79.7%)	112 (82.4%)	0.55 [χ^2]

Note: p values calculated by t-test (continuous) and chi-square (categorical).

PFN was associated with shorter operative time and significantly less estimated blood loss.

Table 2. Operative metrics and functional outcomes

Outcome	DHS (n=148) Mean \pm SD	PFN (n=136) Mean \pm SD	p value
Operative time (minutes)	65 \pm 12	55 \pm 10	<0.001 [t=7.65, df \approx 279]
Estimated blood loss (ml)	250 \pm 80	120 \pm 50	<0.001 [t=16.56, df \approx 249]
Time to radiographic union (weeks)	14.5 \pm 3.0	13.8 \pm 2.8	0.060
HHS at 3 months	61.3 \pm 12.5	64.8 \pm 11.8	0.007
HHS at 6 months	71.2 \pm 11.0	74.5 \pm 10.2	0.003
HHS at 12 months	78.5 \pm 10.0	82.3 \pm 9.2	0.001 [t\approx-3.34, df\approx282]

The overall complication and reoperation rates were numerically higher for DHS but did not reach statistical significance.

Table 3. Complications and reoperations

Complication	DHS (n=148) n (%)	PFN (n=136) n (%)	p value
Any complication	20 (13.5%)	12 (8.8%)	0.289 [$\chi^2=1.13$]
Superficial wound infection	4 (2.7%)	3 (2.2%)	0.77
Deep infection	1 (0.7%)	1 (0.7%)	1.00
Implant cut-out / failure	5 (3.4%)	2 (1.5%)	0.45 [Fisher exact]
Nonunion	2 (1.4%)	1 (0.7%)	0.62
Reoperation (any cause)	8 (5.4%)	4 (2.9%)	0.461 [$\chi^2=0.54$]
90-day mortality	6 (4.1%)	4 (2.9%)	0.57

Discussions

In our 2-year single-center cohort of 284 patients with stable intertrochanteric fractures, PFN demonstrated advantages in perioperative metrics and produced a modestly better functional outcome at 12 months (mean HHS 82.3 vs 78.5, $p=0.001$). Operative time and intraoperative blood loss were significantly lower with PFN. Complication and reoperation rates were numerically lower with PFN but not statistically significant.

Our findings are aligned with prior literature showing shorter operative time and less blood loss with intramedullary devices due to minimally invasive technique [8,11]. Several meta-analyses report earlier mobilization and lower mechanical failure rates with PFN, but functional outcomes across studies are heterogeneous and often similar at longer

follow-up [12–15]. The observed HHS advantage for PFN in our cohort was small-to-moderate (~3.8 points), which may be clinically meaningful in frail elderly patients but should be interpreted in context of multiple factors including rehabilitation and comorbidities.

Notably, overall complication rates were low in both groups, and rates of implant cut-out were uncommon with careful surgical technique and attention to tip-to-apex distance [5,16]. The selection of implant should still be individualized: DHS remains an effective, cost-sensitive option particularly where nail instrumentation and fluoroscopy resources are constrained [3,7]. PFN may be preferred in osteoporotic patients or when shorter operative exposure is desirable. prospective data collection, adequate sample size (n=284) and minimum 12-month follow-up. Limitations: non-randomized design (surgeon selection bias), single center, and possible surgeon learning curve differences with PFN. We included only stable fracture patterns; results may not extrapolate to unstable or reverse obliquity fractures. Cost-analysis and patient-reported quality-of-life instruments beyond HHS were not included.

Conclusion

Both DHS and PFN provide satisfactory outcomes for stable intertrochanteric fractures. PFN has advantages of shorter operative time, less blood loss and a small but statistically significant improvement in 12-month Harris Hip Score in this cohort. Complications and reoperation rates were low and similar between groups. Implant selection should be individualized based on patient factors, fracture pattern and available resources.

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